

Species identification of seafood in China

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Abstract

Seafood is organisms that are served as food by humans. The goal of this study was to find out the biological identity, origins, and distributions of the seafood sold in the market. Seafood specimens were collected, and PCR was used to amplify their COI fragments, and their DNA was used for species identification. 17 out of 40 specimens have been identified, and they ranged across bivalves, cephalopods, fish, crustaceans, and gastropods. All of the identified specimens matched their labels, but not all places of origin labeled matched the species' distribution. More methods could be improved regarding the identification of the origin and provenance of seafood.

1. Introduction

Seafood refers to creatures in the sea that are served as food, mainly consisting of animals such as fish, crabs, shrimp, mollusks, squid, and octopus. They provide many benefits for the human body because of their nutrition; they are rich in proteins, n-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids, and they also contain vitamins, minerals, and trace metals [1].

Seafood available in the market is labeled to provide consumers with more information. These labels usually use the common name of the seafood, as it is the most direct way to provide information to consumers about this commodity. However, many problems still remain about the labeling of seafood. Sellers often give the product a name that purposefully appeals to the consumers; the labels also include mistakes in naming, both unintentionally and intentionally. These actions might seem minor, but they could actually greatly influence consumer decisions as they create a difference between the seafood's label and real identity. This difference could be consequential to the consumers if the perceived seafood is substituted for a lower quality, cheaper, and nutrient-poor alternative [2, 3].

In this study, seafood was collected and sampled from online shopping channels and Japanese restaurants in Nanjing, China, which were then identified using PCR technology to determine the specific species, and the origin of the seafood was predicted, so as to determine the extent to

which seafood substitution is a problem in the market.

2. Method

2.1. Sampling

40 samples were bought at Freshippo's WeChat mini-program and Qianhua Japanese Cuisine [XueZe Road, Nanjing, China]. There were a total of 40 specimens ranging across bivalves, crustaceans, cephalopods, gastropods, and fish (Table. 2). The samples were taken on three separate days. Seven specimens were bought and taken from Qianhua Japanese Cuisine on Xue Ze Road, and 33 specimens were bought and taken from Freshippo's WeChat mini-program; one seafood bought from Freshippo was sampled twice. Photos with IDs and scale bars of the samples were taken. A small part of the specimen was dissected and preserved in a 2 mL centrifuge tube that contained 99.8 percent ethanol. For fish, a piece of meat sample was dissected from the body or the tail. For bivalves, a piece of the foot, the mantle, or the muscle was sampled. For crustaceans, a piece of the abdomen near the tail was sampled. For cephalopods, a piece of the arm was cut off, and for gastropods, a piece of the foot was sampled.

2.2. DNA extraction

Glass beads of 0.03-0.05 mm diameter were added to the centrifuge tube containing the samples, and the samples were ground using a handheld homogenizer. DNA extraction was conducted using the Biospin Marine Animal Genomic DNA Extraction Kit produced by Bioer Technology [Hangzhou, China]. The extraction steps were followed according to the extraction guidelines of the extraction kit, except that Samples 20-40 were not centrifuged at 14,000 g for 3 minutes after being lysed in a 37°C water bath overnight.

2.3. PCR amplification

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The DNA amplified was the mitochondrial gene encoding cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COI). The concentration of the DNA was measured by nanodrop device ND-100C [Miulab, HangZhou, China]. Then, 1 μL (10 nmol/L) of each of the two primers, LCO1490 (5'-GGTCAACAAATCATAAAGATATTGG-3') and HC02198 (5'-TAAACTTCAGGGTGACCAAAAATCA-3'), were mixed with 1-100 nmol/L of DNA template, 22 μL of ddH₂O and 25 μL of 2X Phanta Max Master Mix 1ml Dye Plus from Vazyme [Nanjing, China] to form a total volume of 50 μL for the PCR reaction. The PCR process was as follows: 35 cycles of 1 minute at 95 °C, 1 minute at 40 °C, 95 seconds at 72 °C, and 7 minutes at 72 °C after the 35 cycles. The product of PCR amplification was checked by electrophoresis to check for the correct size of the product band. For product bands that have a size other than around 700 bp, DNA gel extraction was conducted using Tsingke Biotech [Beijing, China] DNA gel extraction kit TSP601-200.

2.4. Data analysis

After receiving the peak value charts tested by BGI Genomics [Shenzhen, China] via Sanger sequencing, Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis Version 11 was used to extract the DNA sequence code and remove the invalid parts. The sequences with the primer LCO 1490 and HCO 2198 were combined to form the DNA sequence of the samples. DNA sequences were tested by NCBI Blast using the Nucleotide BLAST function. The results that were possibly contaminated were not accepted; the rest of the results with above 99.50 percentage identities were accepted, and the names of the species were recorded.

3. Results

3.1. Summary of species sampled

In total, 16 fish specimens, 10 bivalve specimens, 6 crustacean specimens, 5 cephalopod specimens, 2 gastropod specimens, and 1 unknown specimen were collected (Figure on sample (Fig. 1, 2, and 3)). The results of electrophoresis (Fig. 5, 6, 7) of the 40 specimens showed that 17 specimens had bands with the size of 700 bp, indicating successful amplification of the COI fragment; 10 specimens had bands other than the size of around 700 bp, and 13 specimens had no bands shown, indicating unsuccessful PCR.

Out of 40 specimens, the COI fragments of 25 specimens were successfully sequenced and used for species identification, and 17 results (Fig. 1 and 2, S4, S5, S6, S7, S11, S17, S21, S22, S25, S27, S29, S31, S34, S35, S36, S38, S40) tested by NCBI Nucleotide BLAST were accepted (Table. 2); Results that have 0.0 E-value and above 99.50 Per. Ident were accepted. Four identified specimens of bivalves (Fig. 2, S25, S29, S31, S40) covered the families of *Pinnidae*, *Ostreidae*, *Mactridae*, *Veneridae*. S38 was the

only identified gastropod, and it belongs to the family *Muricidae* (Fig. 2). Four cephalopod specimens were identified; S7, S21, and S22 belong to the family *Octopodidae*, and S11 belongs to the family *Ommastrephidae* (Fig. 1). Three crustacean specimens were identified; S4, S6 belong to the family *Pandalidae*, and S17 belong to the family *Penaeidae* (Fig. 1). Five specimens (Fig. 1 and 2, S5, S27, S34, S35, S36) of fish were identified, and they covered the families of *Scombridae*, *Cichlidae*, *Stromateidae*, *Eleotriidae*, *Serranidae*. Errors occurred when some of the COI were blasted. Samples 10, 13, 20, and 23 were identified as organisms that are not sea creatures which could be due to contamination from equipment in the experiment. Samples 24, 28, 30, and 33 were probably cross-contaminated as their BLAST result corresponded to other samples' organisms, which could be due to mishandling of the operator.

3.2. Place of origin of the examined specimens

Most of the species were from the Indo-Pacific region, including *Thunnus obesus*, *Octopus vulgaris*, *Octopus variabilis*, *Atrina pectinata*, *Mactra antiquata*, *Pampus argenteus*, *Rapana venosa*, *Ruditapes philippinarum* (S5, S8, S21, S25, S31, S34, S38, S40). There were also 2 species on the northwest side of the Pacific (S22, S29), 2 species on the east side of the Pacific (S11, S17), 1 in the north of the Pacific (S4), 1 in the North Atlantic (S6), and 1 in freshwaters of Southeast Asia (S35) (Fig. 1, 2). The samples from the Indo-Pacific region were mainly bivalves, with a couple of other mollusks and fish. No sample of crustacean came from the Indo-Pacific (Fig. 4). The species that are distributed in the Indo-Pacific region or near the seas of China can be caught directly from the sea or cultivated in the region. Species that are not located in the regions near China will either need to be introduced and cultivated or be harvested in their area of distribution and sent to China. For example, *Dosidicus gigas* and *Penaeus vannamei* (Fig. 1, S11 and S18) were both from the East Pacific Ocean, but the first one was cultivated in Shandong Province, and the second one was caught in the seas of Ecuador.

4. Discussion

4.1. About the substitution and mislabeling of species

The extent to which seafood substitution in the market is low. All 17 successfully identified species matched the label the business provided, so the rate of substitution and mislabeling is 0%. This may be because the samples were sourced from shops that meet standards, so no serious seafood fraud was observed. In terms of naming seafood species, some of the names provided by the merchants were general; S11, S21, S22, S38 only provided the big classified category for these seafood items, which were not very specific, while some others used common names (S31, S40).

Using a general name or common name is not always a bad thing if it can meet the requirement of indicating true attributes specified in food labeling regulations, as it provides information in a way that is easy to understand [Regulations on the Management of Food Labeling].

4.2. About mislabeling on the place of origin

8 out of 17 of the identified specimens have their distribution match the place of origin given, which is a rate of 47.06 %. There are 5 identified specimens that were not labeled origin by the seller, and 2 identified specimens are hybrid species cultivated (Table. 1). There are some specimens whose species identity and the documented place of origin of the species could not match with the information provided by the supplier shops; for example, in S11, the place of origin given is Shanghai, but the species is distributed in the east Pacific. This could indicate two possible situations: the species could already be produced through aquaculture in China, or the origin labeled is where the product was processed rather than where the raw material was farmed or captured. Regulations of FAO and the provincial government of Guangdong both mentioned that the location of processing could be labeled as the origin, which provides support for the second situation mentioned above [CODEX GENERAL STANDARD FOR THE LABELLING OF PREPACKAGED FOODS] [Rules for Implementation of aquatic product Labeling in Guangdong Province].

Mislabeling of origin cannot be tested by DNA profiling, but other methods such as elemental analysis could determine the seafood's origin; methods of keeping records such as blockchain could also help in tracing seafood provenance [4].

4.3. Some interesting findings

There were two hybrid species, *Oreochromis niloticus* × *Oreochromis aureus* and *Epinephelus fuscoguttatus* × *Epinephelus lanceolatus* (S27 and S36) in the list of seafood. *Oreochromis niloticus* × *Oreochromis aureus* is a hybrid between two types of tilapia and is nicknamed 'Rainbow snapper' in Chinese; in English, it is called red tilapia [5]. It was bred in the 1960s by Israeli farmers to prevent uncontrolled reproduction, and has advantages such as tolerance to cold water [6]. S36 had multiple species in the alignment results of the NCBI nucleotide blast with an E-value of 0.0 and Per. Ident of 100, but they all belong to the genus *Epinephelus* which is groupers, so one among them is selected. *Epinephelus fuscoguttatus* × *Epinephelus lanceolatus* is a hybrid between two types of groupers; it has many advantages such as resistance to diseases and efficiency in growth that make it appealing for commercial purposes [7].

5. Conclusion

To conclude, I found in this study that all of the species accepted for the sample could match the name labeled by the business. Some of the origins of seafood could match their distribution, and some that do not match may have occurred due to mislabeling, and more could be done in tracing seafood origins.

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Table 1: Table of Distribution Matching

Distribution matching		
Matching status	Amount of samples	Percentage of samples
Distribution match label	8	47.06
Distribution not match label	2	11.76
Information Incomplete	7	41.18

Figure 1: Photo of first 22 specimens, collected from Qianhua Japanese Cuisine on Xue Ze Road and Freshippo's WeChat mini-program; all scale bars are 1 cm. a. S1(Salmon), b. S2(Arctic Clam), c. S3(Unknown), d. S4(Shrimp), e. S5(Tuna), f. S6 (Shrimp), g. S7(Octopus), h. S8 and S9(Yesso Clam), i. S10(Cod), j. S11(Squid), k. S12(Scallop), l. S13(Greenland Flounder), m. S14(Black Tiger Shrimp), n. S15(Cuttlefish), o. S16(Argentine Red Shrimp), p. S17(Vannamei Shrimp), q. S18(Vannamei Shrimp), r. S19(Mellow Yellow Croaker), s. S20(Hairtail), t. S21(Octopus), u. S22(Octopus).

Figure 2: Photo of last 18 specimens, collected from Freshippo's WeChat mini-program; all scale bars are 1 cm. a. S23(Capelin), b. S24(Sea Bass), c. S25(*Atrina*), d. S26(*Pangasius*), e. S27(Rainbow Snapper), f. S28(Small yellow croaker), g. S29(Oysters), h. S30(Mackerel), i. S31(Royal Concubine Shell), j. S32(White Clams), k. S33(Abalone), l. S34(Small White Pomfret), m. S35(Bamboo Shell Fish), n. S36(*Epinephelus* spp.), o. S37(Large White Pomfret), p. S38(Conch), q. S39(Meimei), r. S40(Flower clams).

Table 2: The list of samples for species identification

Sample list						
Sample No.	Classification	Given label	Scientific name by COI(per ident of COI)	Given place of origin		Distribution
S1	Fish	Salmon	ID failed	Unknown		
S2	Bivalve	Arctic Clam	ID failed	Unknown		
S3	Mollusca	Unknown	ID failed	Unknown		
S4	Crustacean	Shrimp	<i>Pandalus platyceros</i> (100.00)	Unknown		North Pacific Ocean[WoRMS]
S5	Fish	Tuna	<i>Thunnus obesus</i> (100.00)	Unknown		Indian, Atlantic, Pacific oceans[Biology dictionary]
S6	Crustacean	Shrimp	<i>Pandalus borealis</i> (100.00)	Unknown		North Atlantic[FAO-Shrimps and Prawns of the World]
S7	Cephalopod	Octopus	<i>Octopus vulgaris</i> (100.00)	Unknown		Circumglobal in temperate and tropical seas[sealifebase]
S8	Bivalve	Yesso Clam	ID failed	Weihai, province	Shandong	
S9	Bivalve	Yesso Clam	ID failed	Weihai, province	Shandong	
S10	Fish	Cod	ID failed	Qingdao, province	Shandong	
S11	Cephalopod	Squid	<i>Dosidicus gigas</i> (100.00)	Shanghai		Eastern Pacific[sealifebase]
S12	Bivalve	Scallop	ID failed			
S13	Fish	Greenland Flounder	ID failed			
S14	Crustacean	Black Tiger Shrimp	ID failed			
S15	Cephalopod	Cuttlefish	ID failed			
S16	Crustacean	Argentine Red Shrimp	ID failed			
S17	Crustacean	Vannamei Shrimp	<i>Penaeus vannamei</i> (100.00)	Unknown		Eastern Pacific Ocean[FAO-Species Fact Sheets]
S18	Crustacean	Vannamei Shrimp	ID failed	Ecuador		
S19	Fish	Mellow Yellow Croaker	ID failed			
S20	Fish	Hairtail	ID failed			
S21	Cephalopod	Octopus	<i>Octopus variabilis</i> (100.00)	Beihai, province	Guangxi	Bohai Sea to South China Sea[The Taiwan Malacofauna Database]
S22	Cephalopod	Octopus	<i>Amphioctopus fangsiao</i> (99.65)	Zhoushan, province	Zhejiang	Northwest pacific[sealifebase]
S23	Fish	Capelin	ID failed			
S24	Fish	Sea Bass	ID failed			
S25	Bivalve	Atrina	<i>Atrina pectinata</i> (100.00)	Dalian, province	Liaoning	Indo-West Pacific[The Taiwan Malacofauna Database]
S26	Fish	Pangasius	ID failed			
S27	Fish	Rainbow Snapper	<i>Oreochromis niloticus x Oreochromis aureus</i> (99.64)	Foshan, province	Guangdong	
S28	Fish	Small yellow croaker	ID failed			
S29	Bivalve	Oysters	<i>Magallana gigas</i> (99.82)	Dalian, province	Liaoning	Northwest Pacific[sealifebase]
S30	Fish	Mackerel	ID failed			
S31	Bivalve	Royal Concubine Shell	<i>Mactra antiquata</i> (100.00)	Beihai, province	Guangxi	Indo-West pacific, South of Nigeria[WoRMS]
S32	Bivalve	White Clams	ID failed			
S33	Gastropod	Abalone	ID failed			
S34	Fish	Small White Pomfret	<i>Pampus argenteus</i> (100.00)	East China Sea		Indo-West Pacific[fishbase]
S35	Fish	Bamboo Shell Fish	<i>Oxyeleotris marmorata</i> (100.00)	Qujing, province	Yunnan	Southeast Asia[fishbase]
S36	Fish	Epinephelus spp.	<i>Epinephelus fuscoguttatus</i> x <i>Epinephelus lanceolatus</i> (100.00)	Sanya, province	Hainan	
S37	Fish	Large White Pomfret	ID failed			
S38	Gastropod	Conch	<i>Rapana venosa</i> (100.00)	Dalian, province	Liaoning	Western Pacific[USGS]
S39	Bivalve	Meibei	ID failed			
S40	Bivalve	Flower clams	<i>Ruditapes philippinarum</i> (100.00)	Dalian, province	Liaoning	Indo-Pacific and the Mediterranean[sealifebase]

Categories of Samples Collected

Figure 3: Pie chart for the categories of all of the sample collected.

Distribution of identified species

Figure 4: Bar graph for the distributions of the samples identified.

Figure 5: results of the gel electrophoresis, Samples 1-20: S1(Salmon), S2(Arctic Clam), S3(Unknown), S4(Shrimp), S5(Tuna), S6 (Shrimp), S7(Octopus), S8 and S9(Yesso Clam), S10(Cod), S11(Squid), S12(Scallop), S13(Greenland Flounder), S14(Black Tiger Shrimp), S15(Cuttlefish), S16(Argentine Red Shrimp), S17(Vannamei Shrimp), S18(Vannamei Shrimp), S19(Mellow Yellow Croaker), S20(Hairtail).

Figure 6: results of the gel electrophoresis, samples 21-40: S21(Octopus), S22(Octopus), S23(Capelin), S24(Sea Bass), S25(Atrina), S26(Pangasius), S27(Rainbow Snapper), S28(Small yellow croaker), S29(Oysters), S30(Mackerel), S31(Royal Concubine Shell), S32(White Clams), S33(Abalone), S34(Small White Pomfret), S35(Bamboo Shell Fish), S36(Epinephelus spp.), S37(Large White Pomfret), S38(Conch), S39(Meibe), S40(Flower clams).

Figure 7: results of the gel extraction: S8(Yesso Clam), S12(Scallop), S29(Oysters), S30(Mackerel), S28(Small yellow croaker), S31(Royal Concubine Shell), S32(White Clams), S33(Abalone), S38(Conch)